

THERMAL PROPERTIES OF UNSATURATED POLYESTER COMPOSITES FILLED WITH CORE-SHELL STRUCTURED SILICA AEROGEL

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ABSTRACT

Lightweight-thermal insulation composites were prepared using unsaturated polyester resin and silica aerogel. Preservation of pores in the aerogel was achieved by modification of the silica aerogel into closed pores, core-shell structure. Well-preserved aerogel pores in the UPR composites result in low density as well as the increase of thermal insulation with an increase of vol% of filler. Lowest thermal conductivity of 0.20 W/mK was achieved for composite containing 70 vol% of core-shell silica aerogel, which is about 55% reduction of the thermal conductivity of UPR (0.45 W/mK). The data from TGA show that decomposition proceeds in three steps for neat UPR as well as UPR composites, but the solid residue above 450 °C was considerably higher for filled composites. Addition of CSA has increased the thermal stability of the UPR by lowering the mass loss rate due to the formation of thermal stable char.

1 INTRODUCTION

Silica aerogel – polymer composites are the state of the art for functional engineering aerogel. Many workers have studied the potential of silica aerogel as reinforcement in polymer resins, covering both thermosets and thermoplastics for various potential applications [1]. Due to its ultra-low density (0.1-0.01 g/cm³), low thermal conductivity (0.05 – 0.01 W/mK) and non-combustible property, silica aerogel has been paid much attention over traditional thermal insulation materials like asbestos, calcium silicate, polyurethane foam, etc. Recent studies used silica aerogel as filler/additive in various engineering and specialty thermosets to raise the service temperature and insulation performance [2-6].

Unsaturated polyester resins (UPR) have high demand in building and transportation industries and design of composite structures for both industries requires consideration of human thermal comfort and fire safety. Improvisation of UPR thermal performance by using filler is more cost-effective and low-cost silica aerogel derived from biomass is one of the potential filler that must be considered. Nevertheless, there is a common problem of mixing silica aerogel with liquid resins as intensive immersion of resin into the nano-porous structure of silica aerogel results in the loss of its unique properties. Some studies have demonstrated a direct relationship between the preservation of aerogel pores and thermal performance of the composites [7-9]. To date, different mixing and curing methods were often proposed as a solution to minimize resin intrusion into silica aerogel pores, but no studies focus on modification of the aerogel itself.

This paper carries out an investigation on thermal conductivity and thermal stability of UPR composites filled with silica aerogel derived from rice husk. Prior to the use in this study, the aerogel particles were coated with a thin polymer layer to avoid resin intrusion into the porous structure. Detailed of the aerogel synthesis and modification (i.e. coating) were published elsewhere. The

thermal conductivity was measured using hot-disk method and the thermal stability of the composite was evaluated using thermogravimetric analysis.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Materials

Hydrophobic silica aerogel particles were synthesized from rice husk ash via sodium silicate route and ambient pressure drying. The fluidized bed coating process was used to modify the silica aerogel particles into a core-shell structure consisting of thin polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) shell (i.e. coating) and silica aerogel core. The core-shell aerogel (CSA) has a thermal conductivity of 0.035 W/mK, bulk density of 0.09 g/cm³, shell thickness around 50 μm and the average particle size of 2.0-2.5 mm. Styrenated (35 wt% of styrene) orthophthalic UPR (Brand name: Reversol) was purchased from Revertex Pvt. Ltd. Co., (Malaysia) as the polymer matrix. The resin was pre-accelerated with cobalt promoter for room temperature curing. The resin has hazy pinkish color fairly translucent after curing. Curing was initiated using methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP) with resin to catalyst volume ratio 99:1.

2.2 Preparation of UPR composites

Mixing of the UPR/CSA composites was carried out using open mould casting technique. First, the UPR (Fig. 1(a)) was mixed with CSA (Fig. 1(b)) until it is homogeneously mixed before the catalyst is added to initiate the cross-linking reaction. The composites were poured into a tray of ultrasonic bath to improve filler dispersion before moulded in cylindrical mould (10 mm in diameter) and left cured at room temperature for 24 hours (Fig. 1(c)). Composition of the composites was determined by volume fraction of CSA filler in UPR which is 10, 30, 50 and 70 vol%.

Fig. 1: Photographic images (a) Orthophthalic UPR (b) CSA particles (c) Cured UPR/CSA composite

2.3 Characterization

The morphologies of CSA and UPR/CSA composite were observed under Scanning electron microscopy (VPSEM-S3400N, Hitachi High-Technologies Co., Ltd., Japan). The apparent (bulk) density of composites was determined by weighing samples of known dimensions. The thermal conductivities of the composites were measured using a hot disc thermal constant analyzer (TPS 2500s, Hot Disc AB, Sweden) based on the transient plane source (TPS) method. The composite samples were prepared into a pair of discs with 10 mm-diameter and 5-mm thickness. Measurement was performed at 25 °C. Thermal stability of the composites was evaluated based on weight loss over temperature using thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA, Mettler Toledo Corp., Switzerland) carried out on 10 mg samples under a nitrogen-rich atmosphere with a gas flow rate of 20 ml/min. Samples were heated up to 600 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Characteristics of CSA filler

The SEM image of Fig. 2(a) reveals the interface from the typical individual CSA particle. The interface between the PVA shell (dark grey) and silica aerogel core (light grey) clearly shows the formation of a core-shell structure with the shell thickness is about 50 μm as measured in Fig. 2(b). Thermal stability of the CSA as studied using TGA as shown in Fig. 3 indicates two degradation steps as the material was heated up to 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The first degradation is attributable to the degradation of the PVA shell with a maximum degradation rate as indicated by derivative (DTG) peak at 280 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The second degradation step is marked by a relatively smaller DTG peak near 510 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ involving around 5 wt% weight losses which are contributed by the oxidation of aerogel $-\text{CH}_3$ surface group. The SEM image of Fig. 4 shows the example of 30 vol% CSA in the UPR/CSA composite at $\times 50$ magnifications. The dispersion of the CSA can be recognized based on the image contrast. The bright region actually represents the CSA particles and the morphology shows that the porous structure of aerogel core was preserved from resin intrusion. However, the CSA particles embedded in the matrix exhibit irregular size and shape due to the shrinking of the UPR during curing.

Fig. 2: SEM images (a) An individual CSA particle with revealed interface (b) Thickness of PVA shell for CSA embedded in epoxy

Fig. 3: TGA-DTG curves of CSA particles

Fig. 4: SEM image of CSA particles in UPR matrix

3.2 Thermal conductivity of UPR/CSA composites

The thermal conductivities obtained from hot-disk thermal analyzer for composites containing, 10, 30, 50 and 70 vol% of CSA were plotted in Fig. 5. The data showed that the decrease in thermal conductivity was not linear relative to CSA vol%. Apparently, the value was sharply decreased at 10 vol% and 30 vol% of CSA particles, but become gradual at higher volume fraction. This trend could possibly be influenced by the structural defects of the composites which affect thermal conductivity. These defects include micro-pores, agglomerates, non-uniformity of filler's geometry and imperfect filler-matrix interfaces. Nevertheless, it is clear that the CSA is effective in reducing the thermal conductivity of UPR with an increase of filler volume fraction. For instance, the addition of 70 vol% of CSA has significantly lowered the thermal conductivity of UPR as much as 55%, from 0.45 W/mK to 0.20 W/mK. Lower thermal conductivity is attributed to the higher volume of silica aerogel pores in the composite which effective in restricting heat transfer. In relation to the preservation of aerogel pores by PVA shell, the densities of the composites were determined. Table 1 summarizes the theoretical and measured densities of the composites. It is found that the measured density of UPR/CSA composites were actually comparable to the theoretical density indicating a high degree of pore preservation by the PVA shell from resin intrusion.

Fig. 5: Thermal conductivity of UPR/CSA composites versus vol% of CSA

Table 1. Densities of UPR/CSA composites

Sample	Filler wt% fraction	Density (g.cm ⁻³)	
		Measurement	Calculation
Neat UPR	0	1.53	1.50 ^b
10 vol% CSA ^a	0.7	1.41	1.36
30 vol% CSA	2.5	1.11	1.08
50 vol% CSA	5.7	0.85	0.80
70 vol% CSA	12.3	0.54	0.51

^aDensity of CSA = 0.09 g.cm⁻³

^bDensity as claimed by the manufacturer

3.3 Thermal stability of UPR/CSA composites

TGA describes the extent of mass loss on decomposition which can be used as one indication of composite resistance to heat (i.e. thermal stability). As shown in Fig. 6, the decomposition of UPR is generally divided into three (3) stages. Stage 1 can be described as an initial heating stage where the rate of mass loss was slow as can be seen up to 280 °C. The mass loss was mainly contributed by the release of trapped water and volatilization of uncured substances from UPR. However, there is no obvious difference in term of mass loss rate between the neat UPR and the composites containing CSA. Stage 2 occurred between 280°C – 450°C which attributed to rapid decomposition of UPR polymer involving more than 80 wt% of mass loss. Within this stage, the effect of CSA filler on the thermal stability of the UPR can be observed based on the mass loss rate as indicated by the maximum DTG peak (Fig. 7). Composites containing CSA particles demonstrate lower decomposition rate and higher maximum decomposition temperature as compared to neat UPR, thus supporting an increase in thermal stability. However, there is no obvious difference between the composites containing different vol% of CSA possibly because of heat transfer is more dominant via the matrix. Above 450 °C (Stage 3), the mass loss rate has returned to its baseline due to the formation of solid residue. Composite containing higher vol% of CSA yields a higher amount of solid residue. Meanwhile, the decomposition of neat UPR results in a very small amount of char (less than 2 wt%) as the UPR decomposed mostly via volatilization. On the effect of CSA, it is observed that the addition of CSA can increase solid residue which also means an increase in the physical integrity of the matrix. This solid residue composed mostly thermal stable carbon char which can protect the adjacent unit masses from heat (i.e. decomposition).

Fig. 6: Mass loss versus temperature curves of neat UPR and UPR composites

Fig. 7: Derivative TG curves of neat UPR and UPR composites

4 CONCLUSIONS

UPR composites were prepared by adding 10 vol%, 30 vol%, 50 vol% and 70 vol% of silica aerogel in the form of core-shell structure (CSA). The CSA constitutes PVA shell which effectively acts as a physical barrier to prevent resin intrusion into aerogel pores. This eventually led to lower density as well as increased thermal insulation of the composite with the increase of the CSA vol%. From TGA results, it is found that the addition of CSA has clearly improved the thermal stability of UPR via formation of solid residue. However, no correlation between the vol% of CSA and thermal stability of UPR was observed except on the amount of the final solid residue.

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